

Prediction of FoG in Parkinson's Disease: A Systematic Review

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Abstract— This study presents a systematic literature review on the application of FoG prediction models in patients with Parkinson's disease. To this end, surveys were conducted in four scientific databases, resulting in 202 publications, with only original primary studies being considered. Sixteen publications were selected for the study, which used inertial and plantar pressure sensors and applied classification algorithms, both machine learning and deep learning, either alone or in combination. The models' performance improved; however, some challenges remain regarding class imbalance, computational capacity, and the sensors' usability in everyday use.

Keywords — prediction; Parkinson's disease; freezing of gait.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation and background

One of the most disabling symptoms of PD (Parkinson's Disease) is FoG (Freezing of Gait), which increases the incidence of falls. [1, 2]. The ability to predict FoG episodes could transform the approach to PD management. Predicting these episodes would allow for earlier interventions, such as medication adjustments, targeted physical therapy, or the use of assistive devices, improving patient mobility and safety. Furthermore, reducing falls would contribute to a lower overload on the healthcare system and improve the quality of life of patients and their caregivers.

Thus, the development of prediction methods capable of anticipating the occurrence of FoG has great potential for improving the quality of life of people with PD. In this regard, in recent years, there has been an effort to develop prediction models capable of anticipating FoG episodes in advance, ranging from less than 1 second to 5 seconds. It is important to emphasize that this is not detection, which occurs after the FoG, nor prediction, which uses historical data to predict whether a patient will or won't experience FoG. It is prediction, capable of identifying the occurrence of FoG in real time. Real-time detection enables the development of devices that generate external stimuli to prevent FoG episodes in PD patients.

B. Problem Statement and the Purpose of the Work

In order to further detail the cutting-edge technology presented regarding this highly relevant topic, a systematic literature review was outlined to answer the research's question: "which studies address the prediction of Freezing of Gait (FoG) in individuals with Parkinson's Disease (PD)?"

II. METHOD

A. Criteria for the Papers' Inclusion and Exclusion

To define the inclusion and exclusion criteria for publications, the PICOS method was used, with the following inclusion criteria:

- P (Population/Participants):
 - Individuals diagnosed with Parkinson's Disease (PD), without restriction on age, sex or stage of the disease.
- I (Intervention/Exposure/Interest Factor):
 - The study should focus on methods, models, algorithms or factors that aim to predict the occurrence of "freezing of gait" (FoG) episodes.
 - this includes, but is not limited to:
 - * Use of wearable sensors.
 - * Gait/movement pattern analysis.
 - * Analysis of neuroimaging data (fMRI, PET, EEG, etc.).
 - * Machine learning or artificial intelligence methods applied to prediction.
- C (Comparison):
 - Studies comparing different prediction methods, or evaluating a single prediction method against a gold standard or other group, were included.
- O (Outcome):
 - The main outcome investigated should be the ability to predict "freezing of gait" (FoG).
 - This can be measured by predictive model performance metrics (accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, AUC, F1-score, etc.).
- S (Type of Study/Methodological Design):
 - Original primary studies: (e.g., clinical trials, cohort studies, case-control studies, cross-sectional studies, validation studies of predictive algorithms/models). When any of the study authors participated in the original primary study, they were also considered.
 - Systematic review studies and meta-analyses: These will be included to identify relevant primary studies and avoid duplication of effort, but the main analysis will focus on data from primary studies.

- There will be no minimum sample restriction, but studies with very small samples will be critically evaluated in the quality phase.

To avoid irrelevant studies, the following types of publications will be excluded:

- Articles that focus only on the DETECTION (not prediction) of FoG: Although related, the focus is on identifying FoG at the time of its occurrence, not on predicting its future occurrence.
- Articles that do not explicitly address Parkinson’s Disease: Studies on FoG in other neurological conditions or populations will be excluded.
- Publication Types:
 - Editorials, letters to the editor, news articles, books, book chapters (unless they are relevant systematic reviews and include primary data not found elsewhere).
 - Opinion articles or comments without original data.
 - Opinion articles or commentaries without original data. Conference abstracts (unless the full text can be obtained and meets the other criteria).
 - Duplicate articles (only the most complete and recent version will be kept).

- Language: no language restrictions, as long as reading and understanding are possible.
- Irrelevance to Prediction: articles that only describe FoG, treatments for FoG, or clinical aspects of PD without focusing on FoG prediction.
- Purely theoretical models or prototypes not tested in patients: The study must present data or validations in real patients.

The method adopted to organize the revision was PRISMA, because of the structure the method proposes. Revised articles were sought in the scientific bases Science Direct, PubMed, EBSCO and Web of Science, as seen in figure 1 and table 1. The search term used was “predict” or “prediction” and “Parkinson’s Disease” Or “PD” and “Freezing of Gait” or “FOG”, searched in the title, abstract or keyword within the last 5 years.

Fig. 1. Prisma

Of a total of 202 publications found in the search, 77 were excluded due to duplication. Of the remaining 125, 70 were excluded after title and abstract analysis because they did not meet the PICO criteria. Even with the search terms present, these publications did not aim to develop FoG prediction models in PD patients. Therefore, 55 publications were evaluated in full, of which 39 were excluded. The main reason for exclusion was the use of secondary studies, using databases such as DAPHNET, BXHC, and REMPARK. The most common database used in the publications was DAPHNET. After applying PRISMA, 16 studies were included in the systematic review.

TABLE 1. Number of Articles per Repository

Repository	Quantity
Science Direct	37
PubMed	85
EBSCO	49
Web of Science	31
Total	202

Table 2 presents the 16 publications included in the study. It identifies the author and year, the prediction method, the type of sensors used, and the results of the models’ performance indicators, such as accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, AUC (Area Under the Curve), MPT (Mean Prediction Time), F1-score, balanced accuracy, false positives, and false negatives.

TABLE 2. Detailed Description of the Available Literature.

Author	Method	Sensor	Performance
Debin Huang et al. (2024) [3]	CNN	IMU's	prediction rate = 96.97% false alarm rate = 22.73%
Hemant Ghayvat et al. (2024) [4]	CNN	IMU's	not informed
Pardoel S, Nantel J, Kofman J, Lemaire ED (2022) [5]	RUSBoosting	FPS	accuracy = 94.2% sens = 77.3% spec = 82.9%
Borzì L et al. (2021) [6]	SVM + LDA + LR	IMU's	sens ON(OFF) = 84.1%(85.5%) spec ON(OFF) = 85.9%(86.3%)
Pardoel S et al. (2024) [7]	RUSBoosting	FPS	sens = 77.69% spec = 79.99%
Shalin G et al. (2021) [8]	LSTM	FPS	sens = 72.5% spec = 81.2%
Haussler AM et al. (2024) [9]	pFOG	IMU's	precision = 89% (100 Hz), 87% (60 Hz), 71% (30 Hz)
Pardoel S et al. (2021) [10]	RUSBoosting	FPS	accuracy = 94.0% (0 s threshold), 95.9% (3 s threshold)
Parakkal Unni M et al. (2020) [11]	RF + NN + NB	force platform	minority-vote case: false negative = 0.26 false positive = 0.20 majority-vote case: false positive = 0.16 false negative = 0.29
Naghavi N, Wade E (2022) [12]	DGAD (CNN + transfer learning + K-means)	IMU's	sens = 63.0% spec = 98.6%
Chen Z et al. (2021) [13]	RF	IMU's	false positive = 27% accuracy = 68% MPT = 2.99 s
Pardoel S et al. (2021) [14]	Decision-Tree Ensemble classifier	IMU's + FPS	sens = 85.2% spec = 86.2%
Dvorani A et al. (2021) [15]	SVM + AdaBoost	IMU's	sens = 88.5% spec = 83.3% AUC = 92.8%
Krasovsky T et al. (2023) [16]	wavelet coherence algorithm	IMU's	sens = 98% spec = 42% balanced accuracy = 70%
Ezhilarasi, J.; Senthil Kumar, T. (2025) [17]	FMRCNN	IMU's	sens = 84.21% spec = 88.96% F1-score = 85.13% AUC = 0.916 accuracy = 87.08% precision = 86.13%
Zhang, YQ et al. (2020) [18]	AdaBoost	IMU's	accuracy = 82.7% (patient-dependent) precision = 77.9% (patient-independent)

The selected studies apply both ML (Machine Learning) and DL (Deep Learning) algorithms. ML algorithms such as RUSBoosting, SVM (Support Vector Machine), LDA (Linear Discriminant Analysis), LR (Linear Regression), RF (Random Forest), NB (Naive Bayes), K-means, Decision-Tree Ensemble classifier and AdaBoost are applied in some cases in isolation. [5, 7, 10, 13], in other situations they are applied in conjunction with other DL classifiers [6, 11, 12]. DL classifiers applied in isolation are also observed, such as CNN (Convolutional Neural Network), NN (Neural Network), LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) and FMRCNN (Faster Mask Region-based Convolutional Neural Network) [3, 4, 8, 17], and the application of other strategies, such as the wavelet coherence algorithm [16]. The diversity of applied algorithms demonstrates that this is a field still under development, and that the strategy adopted depends on the research's objective. Another strategy observed is the development of a proprietary algorithm based on existing models such as DGAD (Deep Gait Anomaly Detector), which combined CNN, transfer learning, and K-means to obtain a more accurate classifier [12].

The selected studies share some common characteristics, such as the use of wearable sensors that are accurate but also lightweight and comfortable, allowing for everyday use. The most common sensors are IMUs (Inertial Measurement Units), but there is a trend toward studies using FPS (Foot Pressure Sensors), which are used in insoles, making them an excellent option for everyday use by patients with Parkinson's disease. IMUs are positioned on different parts of the body, such as the legs, torso, feet, and back of patients. Overall, no significant differences in the performance of the models are observed based on the body part where the sensors are positioned.

Although DL algorithms outperform ML algorithms, there is a concern about computational capacity, since a common objective of the studies is to develop a device capable of predicting FoG episodes before they occur.

An important feature to highlight is the small number of volunteers in the studies and the prevalence of data collections conducted in a controlled environment. Among all the studies, the one with the largest number of volunteers for data collection was 20 [4]. On the other hand, there was a study with only seven volunteers [12], which makes it difficult to generalize the results, requiring an increase in the number of volunteers in future studies.

A common strategy among studies is to label data as FoG and pre-FoG for the application of classification algorithms, whether ML or DL. Another common feature is the application of sliding windows in addition to signal filters during the data processing phase to capture both frequency and time characteristics.

V. CONCLUSION

The trend is toward using FPSs in addition to the IMUs already in use, sometimes in conjunction with them, to improve model performance and capture gait changes that precede FoG episodes. The use of DL algorithms has

increased, sometimes in conjunction with ML algorithms. However, there are concerns about the computational capacity required by these algorithms, given that the goal is to develop devices for daily use by PD patients. To achieve this, these devices need to be more accessible, both in terms of computational capacity and comfort and usability.

The main limitations of these studies are the restricted number of volunteers enrolled in the data collection phase and the prevalence of studies conducted in controlled laboratory environments, with observational studies still being quite limited. Although improved model performance has been observed, some challenges remain regarding class imbalance, computational capacity, and the usability of sensors for everyday use.

VI. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS

A. Statement of informed Consent

Not applicable, as this is a literature review.

B. Statement of human and animal rights

Not applicable, as this is a literature review.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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